

Algorithmic and interpretive moves in identifying NGI Forward key topics

Alberto Cottica (Edgeryders); Kristóf Gyódi (University of Warsaw); Ida A. Nissen (Aarhus University); Michał Paliński (University of Warsaw)

About this document	2
1. Introduction	2
2. A common step: a cross-WP focus group to compare findings	6
3. Key topic identification via digital ethnography and network analysis on own-forum discussion data	7
3.1 Context	7
3.2 Generating the primary data	7
3.3 Ethnographic coding: generating the secondary data	8
3.4 Building the semantic social network	8
3.5 Semantic social network analysis	9
4. Key topic identification via social media analysis centered on human rights online	13
4.1 Focus on human rights on the internet	14
4.2 Identification of an official document	15
4.3 Seeding list	15
4.4 Reddit dataset	15
4.5 Trend reservoir model	16
4.6 Trending topics	17
5. Identification of emerging technologies, social issues and mapping topics based on text-mining	18
5.1 Trend analysis	19
5.2 Term frequencies	21
5.3 Co-occurrence analysis	22
5.4 Sentiment analysis	23
5.5 Topic modelling	24
5.6 Topic mapping	26
References	30

About this document

In the course of the final year of the NGI Forward project¹, three of its partners (DELab and the University of Aarhus, in WP1; and Edgeryders, in WP2) have been working on identifying the overarching issues that kept resurfacing when considering the evolution of Internet technology. That work has been done independently as per the project's Description of Action, but the partners have kept comparing notes. In autumn 2021 it had become clear that our methods, though different, were similar enough for a systematic comparison. We decided to coordinate in writing an extra paper to contain such a comparison. The comparative perspective, we find, brings clarity and accountability to our respective research workflows.

This document is that paper. We intend it as an add-on to our work on topic identification in NGI Forward, contained in more detail elsewhere (Christensen et al. 2021, Hassoun et al. 2021, Nissen et al. 2021), as well as a stand-alone paper on the epistemology of doing data science on social phenomena as captured by test data.

The authors benefited from funding under the Horizon 2020 programme, grant n. 825652.

1. Introduction

The philosophy of science teaches us that claims of objectivity in the sciences – even the hard sciences – are to be taken with great caution. The investigation of any phenomenon depends on its measurement, and what is being measured is informed by an imposition of meaning on its nature. It's only when such investigation is sufficiently mature that scientists can attempt what Chang (2004) calls a "move to the abstract": an understanding of the phenomenon in question that does not depend on measurement techniques. For example, temperature was long understood as the effect of the environment (like a fire pit) on a given substance (like iron). The move to the abstract consisted, in this case, in the modern explanation of temperature as the mean kinetic energy of that substance's particles. It remains uncertain whether moves to the abstract are possible in social sciences.

In the absence of moves to the abstract, social researchers continue to understand phenomena in terms of what they measure, and measure what they believe they understand. By implication, interpretation can not be confined to results: interpretive moves are necessary across the whole research workflow. Here, we focus mainly on three phases of research.

The first one, that concerns researchers not generating their own data, is data selection. A tenet of data science is re-using, in new and creative ways, data generated for purposes other than one's research. For example, call data records of phone companies are used to map social networks (Eagle et al. 2010). When that happens, researchers work with information that was generated contextually to the problem it was meant to solve: in the case of call data records, billing a phone company's customers. Attempting to use the same data for something else is

¹ <https://research.ngi.eu/>

almost certain to introduce biases: for example, the part of people's social networks not involving phone calls is not captured by the dataset. Acknowledging and understanding these biases and how they influence results is essential for good research. In NGI Forward, a recurring concern has been that available datasets tend, to various degrees, to over-represent the tech-savvy part of the European population and to under-represent minorities at risk of social exclusion.

The second one concerns the processing of data before modeling, often called "data cleaning". Far from being a purely technical, automatizable phase, data cleaning involves decisions on what, in the data, counts as valuable information, and what is treated as noise. Apparently innocent decisions on what to omit from a dataset may lead researchers to fundamentally different conclusions (Decuyper et al. 2016).

The third one is modeling itself. In recent years, research has documented how researchers, starting from the same data and investigating the same question, arrive at different conclusions in controlled environments (Silberzahn et al. 2018; Breznau et al. 2021). Researchers' skill and confirmation biases, and explicit decisions made in research teams (used as regressors in the study by Breznau and collaborator) may play a role, but, like for data cleaning, it seems clear that most of the variance in results is caused by idiosyncratic modeling choices².

In the case of NGI Forward, an additional element that influences our research is the nature of the project as part of the European Commission's Next Generation Internet Initiative. NGI Forward's mandate is to assist the Commission in developing a strategy for its technology policy in the area of Internet technologies³. The Commission's agenda and priorities clearly influence those of the project in foregrounding what matters, and are in turn influenced by the political debate on the Internet in Europe.

We respond to this epistemological uncertainty by falling back on the rigour and accountability of our data analysis process. First, we subscribe to a relational view of data and data work (Leonelli 2019). This view acknowledges that data are not immutable objects encoding reality in any objective way. Rather, objects (such as call data records) are *made* into data in the context of a specific research addressing a specific question⁴ (figure 1).

² "[...] the massive variation in reported results originated from unique or idiosyncratic decisions in the data analysis process, leaving 95.2% of the total variance in results unexplained [...] We have tapped into a hidden universe of idiosyncratic research and researcher variability." (Breznau et al. 2021)

³ <https://www.ngi.eu/ngi-projects/ngi-forward/>

⁴ "[...] data are only such by virtue of their function within a given situation of inquiry, and their relationship to the inquirer, the nature of the phenomenon being investigated and other components (such as relevant models and algorithms)." (Beaulieu and Leonelli 2021)

Figure 1. A relational perspective of data (source: Leonelli 2019)

Second, we keep track of what anthropologists call our own positionality, i.e. how we stand with respect to the issues being investigated, what our histories are with respect to them, and how these might be introducing biases in our work.

And third, we make a point of describing in detail our methodological decisions, in all three phases of data selection, data cleaning and modeling itself. In the rest of the document, we proceed to do this, organizing the argument around tasks. The document offers no conclusion, since it is only meant as a device for accountability and reflexivity.

Figure 2. Different pathways to topic identification in NGI Forward

2. A common step: a cross-WP focus group to compare findings

In March 2021 we convened a dedicated consortium meeting to compare notes across WP1 and WP2. All consortium partners were represented. The process used was similar to that of focus groups: a group of research partners, immersed in not-yet- or only-partially processed data, had noted patterns and salient keywords about those data. A group of policy partners attempted a mapping of those patterns and keywords onto the policy debate, for our results to be better legible and reusable by policy makers. In other words, the partners constituted a sort of focus groups of experts on the state of the debate on the Next Generation Internet. The final result was six key topics:

1. Environment, Sustainability and Resilience
2. Decentralising Power and Building Alternatives
3. Public Space and Sociality
4. Privacy, Identity, and Data Governance
5. Trustworthy Information Flows, Cybersecurity and Democracy
6. Access, Inclusion and Justice

These labels are not in the “raw” data. They were created during the meeting as the result of a clustering of related, but more granular, issues that were in the raw data, such as “Environmental impact of devices” and “Justice and Digital Discrimination”. Figure 2 shows the digital board we produced during the meeting, populated with the issues grouped into topics:

Figure 3. The digital board summarizing the results of the March 2021 focus group.

In the final year of the project, this shared view functioned as a lens through which to view our respective data. It reflected what we expected to find at the end of the analysis; additionally, policy partners assured us that these were all top-of-the-agenda issues, on which expert knowledge would be welcome in the policy space. They broadly defined the directions in which we were looking.

3. Key topic identification via digital ethnography and network analysis on own-forum discussion data

In WP2 (tasks 2.1 through 2.6), led by Edgeryders, we hosted a public forum (NGI Exchange) on the future of the Internet. This was meant to be a participatory exercise, open to all, foregrounding civil society activists, hacker communities and just interested citizens over credentialed experts and “usual suspects” of European policy debates. The results of that activity are summarized in Deliverable 2.5.

As a byproduct, this research also generated groups of concepts, amenable to be summarized as key topics in the sense of WP1.

3.1 Context

The NGI Exchange forum had its own visual identity and third-level domain (<https://exchange.ngi.eu>), but it branched out from the pre-existing Edgeryders community and was, and still is, hosted on the forum of Edgeryders. Many of the 338 participants in the conversation joined the forum for the specific purpose of participating in NGI Exchange, but many others joined from other conversations in Edgeryders.

The Edgeryders online community counts about 7,000 accounts at the time of writing. It has its roots in digital culture as it appeared in the first decade of this century. As the name indicates, it tends to attract people with a high tolerance for technical and social change, and a certain sympathy for the practices of knowledge sharing of the early Internet. While a good fit for the objectives of WP2 to go “beyond the usual suspects”, it is obviously not representative of the European population as a whole.

3.2 Generating the primary data

WP2 generated its own primary data in tasks T2.1 through T2.3. By this expression, we mean the 4,100 forum posts that make up the corpus for the NGI ethnography. The process of generation consisted in opening an online forum, and seeding it with “conversation starters”: high-quality posts, often written by people with some standing in certain communities, that highlighted a potentially relevant angle on Internet technology while still being grounded in human experience (as opposed to, for example, commercial messages)⁵. The conversation

⁵

An

example:

<https://edgeryders.eu/t/a-radically-new-internet-a-study-on-p2p-protocols-and-mesh-networks/9802>.

starters and other interesting posts that the fledgling community produced were reshared on social media (especially Twitter) in a bid to attract more participants and gather more points of view. On the forum itself, community managers made sure that participants felt welcome and appreciated, asked questions, and connected threads to each other. The goal of this activity was to have a plurality of points of view in every discussion.

Given all that, the discussions we ended up with were influenced by the conversation starters, which in turn were influenced by the political priorities that inspired the Next Generation Internet initiative at large, and by the mission of WP2 to involve unusual suspects, like Indieweb enthusiasts and privacy activists. Another influence was the social networks of key Edgeryders staff, that carried the signal of the conversation starters into the broader public via social media.

All in all, the data generation phase has been highly interpretive, with a plurality of actors (the project officer, the NGI community at large, in turn communicating with DG CNECT, project staff) having to make decisions at every step about what mattered, what was worth debating.

3.3 Ethnographic coding: generating the secondary data

In this phase (T2.4), professional ethnographers read the corpus and annotated it as needed, associating the content with a limited number of ethnographic codes. Coding activity followed the tenets of grounded theory (Glaser and Strauss 1968). This activity resulted in about 6,000 annotations, that makes use of 1,000 codes. These codes constitute the ontology of the NGI Exchange conversation. Annotations and codes are used as secondary data in the following steps of the research process.

This phase, too, is interpretive, given that each annotation is the result of the ethnographer interpreting the informant's post on the forum.

3.4 Building the semantic social network

In this phase, a Python script builds an interpretable network of relationships between the relevant entities in the study, like participants and ethnographic codes. This network maps several types of relationships across entities: for example, authorship (from participants to the posts they wrote) and annotation (an annotation concerns a certain post). Through a technique called projection we transformed this network into one where all edges encode *one single* type of relationship, that of co-occurrence of codes. Two codes A and B are said to co-occur if each of them is associated to at least one annotation, and if at least one annotation associated to A and one associated to B are annotations of the same post.

We interpret this network as a pattern of associations. The concepts expressed by the codes have been associated in the forum post that was annotated with both A and B, and we represent this association with an undirected edge linking A to B. Two codes can co-occur more than once, giving rise to deeper association. We define the *association depth* between two codes as the count of co-occurrences between those codes occurring across all posts in the corpus.

Association depth is encoded as the weight of the edge e connecting the two codes, and indicated by $d(e)$. The resulting network is weighted and undirected. We call it the codes co-occurrence network (CCN). The CCN of this corpus has the 1,000 codes as nodes⁶, connected by about 40,000 co-occurrence edges.

Another projection operation maps the social network of interactions across participants in the NGI Exchange forum. Here, edges represent replies. This network is directed (Alice replies to Bob is not the same as Bob replying to Alice) and weighted, since Alice could reply to Bob several times. The interaction across participants is the social mechanism that spreads ideas and points of view, and puts them out for validation and improvement ahead of the ethnographic coding phase. The social interaction network has the 338 participants as nodes, connected by about 900 interaction edges.

This phase of the process is algorithmic, but it still involves interpretation in that the networks generated by the projection are claimed to have a straightforward interpretation (Cottica et al. 2020).

3.5 Semantic social network analysis

Semantic social network analysis (SSNA) is an iterative phase, where the researcher manipulates the graph (mostly its CCN projection) to spot patterns and generate hypotheses, and then goes back to the raw data to confirm or deny her intuition (Cottica et al. 2020). The main algorithmic moves are:

- filter the CCN, leaving out shallow associations.
- run community identification algorithms on the reduced CCN.

While these moves are algorithmic, the key parameters that the algorithms need to run are guided by interpretation. Based on having read the corpus, does it make sense to reduce the CCN from 1,000 nodes and 6,000 edges, to, like below, 200 nodes and 700 edges? Are we leaving anything important out? The choice is made on the basis of interpreting the reduced graph in the light of the corpus.

Doing SSNA on the NGI XChange ethnographic corpus has meant, for us, using the CCN to guide our interpretation of the underlying qualitative data. We did this in two principal ways. The first, is to use a strongly reduced version of the network (as described above) as a way to perceive the pattern of connectivity at a high level of description. The second is to inspect the CCN more locally, typically in the vicinity of salient codes like artificial intelligence. In this second type of analysis, free from the need to take in the whole corpus in a single glance, we were able to analyze our data in a richer way, pulling back in associations that were not the absolute strongest in the graph.

⁶ In the rest of this section, we use the term “codes” when referring to the nodes of the CCN, which indeed represent ethnographic codes. When we refer to networks in general (for example, to describe algorithms that work on any network) we use the term “nodes”.

We also used SSNA to identify the five overarching topics mentioned in the Topic Areas section. We proceeded as follows.

1. Induce a human-interpretable CCN. Following the literature on network visualization (Ghoniem 2004; Melançon 2006; Munzner 2014) define “human interpretable” as a graph with at most a few hundred nodes, and whose number of edges is at most four times the number of its nodes. We take the whole codes co-occurrence network, rank its edges by importance, and start discarding the least important edges until we hit a graph with low enough density. We define importance as association breadth, the number of informants who authored at least a contribution coded with the two codes. We chose to reduce the network by filtering out all edges induced by fewer than 25 co-occurrences. The resulting reduced CCN has 203 codes, connected by 699 co-occurrence edges.
2. Compute the reduced network’s maximal modularity partition (Blondel et al. 2008). This is a way to resolve the network into communities of nodes, where each node is more connected to the nodes in its community than to nodes in other communities. We also keep track of the modularity value. If it is close to zero, the whole exercise makes little sense: the network is indistinguishable from random, there are no meaningful communities of nodes. Visualize the network obtained, with color coding for the different nodes communities (technically, the classes of the maximal modularity partition). The network resulting from this process is highly modular ($C = 0.55$).
3. For each community, make a list of the nodes in it.

Additional interpretive moves in this type of analysis are:

4. In each community of codes, the (topologically) central ones in the cluster define the semantics of the cluster itself: “this part of the conversation is about AI”, for example.
5. The more peripheric codes in the same community encode information on which concepts the informants associate to the defining ones in the center. Some novelty can be looked for here. For example, researchers can make observations like “artificial intelligence is connected to public spaces by way of smart cities”.
6. The codes that stand at the margin between two communities function as logical connectors. Again, some meaning can be glimpsed, like in exploitative business models joining up the AI and the business models communities of codes.

Applying the reduction method described above, we find that, if we filter out all edges e , $d(e) < 25$, we are left with a reduced CCN with 203 nodes and 699 edges, not that different from the previous case. It is shown in figure 4 (brighter edges map to broader depth of association):

Figure 4. The reduced codes co-occurrence network of the NGI Xchange corpus. Edges encode a minimum of 25 co-occurrences. Brighter edges map to a higher number of co-occurrences.

The network's maximal modularity partition is shown in figure 3. The classes of the partition are 9. Some correspond to small connected components to the east and the north of the graph; the giant component has three large communities with 63, 49 and 38 nodes respectively, and two smaller ones with 24 and 18 nodes, respectively.

Figure 6. Algorithmically defined communities of codes are semantically consistent

The five communities of codes identified in the giant component of the reduced CCN identify each a key topic area. These are: **“The Future of Work” (Pink)**, **“Data, Privacy & Control” (Grey)**, **“Big Tech, Regulation, and Business Modes” (Orange)**; **“Crisis, Resilience & Environmental Sustainability” (Lavender, plus some grey codes)**, and **“Artificial Intelligence, Algorithmic Inequality & Justice” (Blue)**.

The topic area “Crisis, Resilience & Environmental Sustainability” is the only one whose key codes span across different partitions. We believe that its identification is, nevertheless, appropriate and methodologically consistent because (1) these codes are indeed associated, albeit at lower levels of association depth than those that allow a network reduction sufficient to make the reduced CCN amenable to visual analysis; (2) over the coding period, the CCN has naturally shifted as we merged, split, and renamed codes, and during many phases these codes were more strongly associated than they ended up being in the final analysis.

4. Key topic identification via social media analysis centered on human rights online

As part of WP1, in the last year of NGI Forward, Aarhus University finalized a final social media analysis report (D1.8), a topic guides and evaluation criteria report (D1.10), and two workshops

(D1.14 and D1.15). The current paper relates mainly to the decisions taken for the final social media report, as that work informed the other deliverables. An overview of this section is presented in figure 5.

Figure 7: Overview of the different interpretative and algorithmic steps in AU’s tasks in work package 1 in the last year of NGI forward. We started with a focus on human rights online, which informed our two workshops as well as our final social media analysis report.

4.1 Focus on human rights on the internet

The largest deliverable (D1.8) for AU was a final social media analysis, where the goal according to the grant agreement was to analyze several social media platforms to identify the discussed internet-related topics. This goal was very broad and we presented our intermediary results at the midterm review in October 2020. One of the main feedback we got from the reviewers was that we should not only focus on the discussions about internet technology, but put more emphasis on the social aspect of the internet. This would supplement the technology-centered focus of the first phase of our work for the NGI project.

This feedback led us to take the first and major interpretative step: the choice to focus on human rights on the internet. We made this choice based on NGI’s mission to shape the future internet according to European values like openness, inclusivity, democracy and equality. Human rights align with those European values, and we have therefore chosen to focus on them as they provide a social dimension to our analysis. By incorporating human rights on the internet instead of the broader human rights, we kept the analysis relevant for internet technology and the next generation internet.

4.2 Identification of an official document

The first step was to identify an official document that described human rights on the internet, which we could use to extract relevant keywords. We found a fitting document in the 'Charter of Human Rights and Internet Principles', which was launched in 2011 and revisited in 2013. It was published by the Internet Rights and Principles Coalition (IRPC), which is based at the UN Internet Governance Forum. This was a qualitative choice and motivated by the document being UN-based and its specificity and inclusivity of the European values mentioned above. The document has been condensed into ten key internet rights and principles (<http://internetrightsandprinciples.org/site/campaign>), which are grounded on international human rights standards. Those ten key rights and principles provided the basis for extracting keywords that were relevant to human rights on the internet.

4.3 Seeding list

The next step was to extract keywords from the ten key rights and principles document. This process is described in more detail in our paper 'Human rights and internet principles report' ([Human Rights and Internet Principles Seeding List | Zenodo](#)). Each right or principle was condensed into a shorter statement that included the right or principle itself and a specification of the environment, for example: freedom and equality online; access to a secure and open internet. Subsequently, each statement was divided into keywords, with the aim to be as concise as possible (e.g. freedom online, equality online, access to secure internet, access to open internet). Both the condensation of the ten key rights and principles into short statements and further into keywords were interpretive steps, which were performed by one researcher and agreed upon with another researcher. With those interpretative choices made by the researchers we could add the social aspect to the technological internet research. The seeding list was used to connect human rights online to the development of technologies and to the internet.

4.4 Reddit dataset

The keywords of the seeding list were used as a query in Reddit's search engine to find relevant subreddits. From the 304 returned subreddits, we selected 49 subreddits as being relevant. This selection included interpretative steps, namely the establishment of exclusion criteria and the estimation of the subreddit's relevance. The exclusion criteria were a list of six points, which were established based on the content of the returned 304 subreddits. The exclusion criteria were any subreddits that belonged to any of the following categories: 1. Service provider and/or technical support; 2. Gaming online or manga series; 3. NSFW; 4. Politics and/or news; 5. Private or single member; 6. Public person. We deemed those categories irrelevant for the discussion of trending internet technology and we therefore excluded them. For those subreddits that were left, we estimated their relevance based on two criteria: 1. discussion concerning digital or internet technologies and 2. discussion related to human rights and values. These two inclusion criteria were established with the goal of NGI in mind: to find trending topics about internet technology and associated social issues. For the latter, we had chosen to

focus on human rights online, which is reflected in the second inclusion criterion. Of the 49 selected subreddits, 12 were re-occurrences, resulting in a total of 37 subreddits discussing issues relating to human rights on the internet. While both the exclusion and inclusion criteria were established using interpretation, we nonetheless listed the criteria enabling us to follow them objectively and ensure reproducibility of our results.

Of the 37 relevant subreddits, we excluded those with less than 120 posts and comments for an accurate estimation of the topic distribution. This decision was based on prior experience with the applied topic model, as too few entries do not allow for an accurate result. Furthermore, two subreddits were excluded because of errors in the analysis pipeline, which yielded 17 subreddits for the analysis.

4.5 Trend reservoir model

To detect topics that are trending, we applied a trend reservoir model on the subreddit dataset. Even though this analysis step was algorithmic, several interpretative decisions had to be made in the process. Further details on the methodological parts can be found in the deliverable D1.8 (final social media analysis report).

Before applying the model, the text in the subreddits was preprocessed. This included cleaning the text, lemmatization, removing stop words, tokenizing, and removing empty tokens. The exact choices of what to remove and which algorithm to use for lemmatization and tokenizing (we used SpaCy, Honnibal & Montani, 2017) were strictly speaking interpretative, but we used a commonly used pipeline and an established standard procedure.

Several subreddits (n=7) were very large, which posed a challenge to our available computational capacities. We therefore downsampled the subreddits based on their timestamp by allocating the posts into time bins of 30 minutes. This choice made by the researchers was based on balancing computational time with keeping a good time resolution. However, the two largest subreddits (conspiracy and technology) did not run through due to processing errors.

The trend estimation model is based on the topic distribution of each post and comment in the subreddit. We used latent Dirichlet allocation (LDA) (Blei et al. 2003) to estimate the topic distribution, which is a commonly used method. The LDA model requires the number of topics as input, which is usually selected from a range of tested topic numbers based on the largest coherence score. We chose to test the topic numbers 20, 30, 50 and 80 (for the downsampled subreddits, it was 100, 500, 1000, 1500 and 3000, due to each document containing more text). Here, the choice of topic number range was interpretative, but the testing and selection of the optimal topic number was algorithmic.

The trend potential of each subreddit is based on the concepts of novelty, transience and resonance. Those concepts measure the change of topics over time, namely how much new content is introduced (novelty), and how much topics stick or disappear (transience). A combination of the two measures to what extent topics are both novel and sticky (resonance)

(Barron et al. 2018; Nielbo et al. 2020). For this comparison of topic distribution over time, the data is divided into time windows of three consecutive posts. This interpretative choice was based on previous experience with applying the trend reservoir model to other datasets. This choice is exemplary for the choices researchers applying algorithmic methods often have to make: parameters have to be set, and while a limited range of parameter values can be tested, the subjective experience gained by this testing often determines the preferences for certain parameter values. The chosen parameters can influence the final results, but testing them rigorously is often time consuming (especially when combinations of parameters are to be tested) or might not be simple due to the lack of clear evaluation criteria for the results.

4.6 Trending topics

Subreddit discussions with trend potential had a large value of the novelty-resonance slope, which was obtained after plotting resonance as a function of novelty and estimating the linear slope coefficient. A large value of the novelty-resonance slope indicated a novel and sticky content of the subreddit. To obtain the trending topics within each subreddit, we calculated the novelty-resonance slope over time. For this we divided the novelty and resonance time series into sliding windows of 21 datapoints and fitted a linear line to each window, which gave us a time series of the slope values. The choice of a sliding window was made to preserve the slight change in discussed topics over time and the choice of 21 datapoints was based on previous experience with 21 being the minimum to obtain reliable results (see the discussion on parameter choice based on experience in the section above).

As our aim was to identify the trending topics, which had a high novelty-resonance slope, we had to set a threshold for what 'a high slope' would be. We chose this threshold to be the top 10% of the slope values for each subreddit, which was an interpretative trade-off between having sufficient datapoints for the subsequent topic model and not selecting too many of the documents (one window in the top 10% constituted of 21 novelty and resonance time points, which in turn contained three documents). We applied a topic model to those top 10% posts for each subreddit, to obtain the topics of those trending documents. The topic model (LDA) returned the topics present in the subreddits together with the top keywords that described each topic, and we chose the top 10 keywords for finding a title. Those last steps are again interpretative, to choose the top ten keywords and the choice of a topic title given those keywords. Especially selecting the topic title required an interpretation of the keywords to find a meaningful and inclusive title. However, the delivery of the keywords by the LDA model was algorithmic. The LDA also returned the post with the highest probability of matching the topic best, which we used to interpret the meaning of the keywords in context. This use of our model exemplifies how algorithmic and interpretative steps go hand in hand, and shows that algorithms seldom work in isolation.

For the results, we chose to look at the three most representative topics for each subreddit. This choice was made to focus the results on the most important and most present topics within a subreddit. We further condensed the findings (three topic titles for each of the 17 analysed

subreddits) into overarching topics with subtopics. This was done by qualitatively labelling the identified trending topics, which required interpretation of the found topic titles and their relation. This last step was difficult, as some topic titles were more specific and clear-cut than others. However, several topics were clearly related, and we therefore decided to organize the topics into overarching topics in order to summarize our findings. To conclude, we found that six overarching topics emerged from the trending topics: 'privacy', 'censorship', 'alternatives to mainstream internet services', 'internet security', 'hacking', and 'cryptocurrency'. Those topics with their subtopics are depicted in figure 6.

Figure 8: A summary of the identified trending topics with subtopics. The topics and subtopics were qualitatively summarized from the topics discovered with the topic model. The sizes of the topics do not convey popularity of topics. This figure was originally published in the deliverable D1.8 final social media analysis report.

5. Key topic identification based on text-mining

The following sections provide a brief overview of the methodologies developed by DELab. A more elaborate version of these sections can be read at deliverable D1.12 : Final open data sets & code, and methodology guides.

Throughout NGI Forward, we have been pursuing two complementary approaches to examine technology and policy issues with the help of text-mining techniques. Our first proposition focused on the identification of emerging issues gaining importance over time: we refer to this methodology as *trend analysis*. The aim of the second approach is to map specific topics discussed in online documents - we call it *topic mapping*. The two approaches have a key

difference: in trend analysis we do not have any prior assumptions on what topics we want to analyse, while for topic mapping a preliminary selection of broad areas of investigation are necessary. As an example, if we are interested in gaining insights on a defined problem, such as privacy or climate change, topic mapping provides more suited solutions. On the other hand, if we would like to highlight issues gaining traction, trend analysis provides the necessary tools. Let us briefly explain the main steps and assumptions of the two methodologies.

5.1 Trend analysis

In the case of trend analysis we focus on capturing terms with increasing frequency in news websites. A crucial question is the selection of sources: how to select the sample of documents for the analysis. As explained in our working paper (Gyódi et al. 2019), the initial sample of technology news websites was selected based on a set of inclusion criteria:

- they reported on emerging technologies in the past (e.g. on blockchain in the period 2010-2012)
- they cover a wide range of tech topics
- they are based in the EU / US

The list of media sources has been consistent throughout the duration of the project with 14 websites (Gyódi et al. 2021a).

The main aim of trend analysis is to capture terms gaining traction in text documents. Additionally, our methodology also includes further tools to map and explore emerging topics. The trend analysis consists of four main steps:

- Term frequencies
- Co-occurrences
- Sentiment analysis
- Topic modelling

The proposed pipeline enables the exploration of issues at different levels. First, we identify trending terms based on the analysis of term frequencies. The most trending terms can be highlighted using regression analysis. These identified terms are the basis for further analysis. The co-occurrence analysis presents pairs of terms that are most frequently mentioned together, finding connections between relevant topics. In order to track the public perception of issues and identify the positive and negative news stories related to a selected topic, sentiment analysis is performed. To additionally verify our results, topic modelling is prepared using Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA). LDA shows which terms define key topics across the text corpus, providing information on broad topics and co-occurrences. In practice, LDA helps understanding the hidden (latent) topics in discussions.

To illustrate the process, we use the results from the trend analysis in 2020⁷.

Figure 9. Main steps of trend analysis

⁷ <https://fwd2020.delabapps.eu>

5.2 Term frequencies

In trend analysis we assume that there is a significant relationship between the importance of an issue and the frequency it is being mentioned. As an example, if the term “5G” is relatively more frequently mentioned (e.g. its share among all terms increased) over time, it indicates that news articles cover more intensively issues related to 5G. Therefore, the basis of trend analysis is the calculation of term frequencies: for each term and source, the average monthly term frequency has been calculated. Besides the frequency of single terms (unigrams), we also calculated the frequency of bigrams - two terms next to each other (e.g. ‘fake news’). Afterwards, the weighted average of frequencies by source has been calculated. Therefore, we make further assumptions related to weighting the different sources in an interpretive step of the analysis. There are significant differences in the number of articles published across the sources: the smallest publisher accounts for less than 1% (Euractiv) of all articles, while the largest makes up more than 20% (Techcrunch). Does this mean that a source is 20 times more relevant than another? Similarly, the majority of articles in our dataset are published by websites in the US, while the smaller publishers of the dataset are based in the EU. On the other hand, the debate in European media may be more relevant for the project. For these considerations, we have assigned weights to ensure that smaller publishers have a greater influence on the results than their share of publications would determine (Gyódi et al., 2021a). We also tested results for the alternative method of assigning equal weight for all sources and found that weighting sources perform better than unweighted⁸.

Following the calculation of the weighted term frequencies, we identified the most trending terms with a regression analysis. The result is a single coefficient for each term that highlights the direction (increase or decrease) and magnitude in the changes in frequencies over time.

Next, the terms were sorted based on the coefficient, enabling the identification of the most trending terms. Therefore, the first stage of the analysis ends with identifying the most significantly growing terms.

The next step is interpretive: we receive a list of trending terms, highlighting technologies, companies, events, and policy proposals. During each iteration of preparing the analysis (we have updated the results multiple times during the project), we reviewed the top 1000 most trending terms, selected the ones most relevant to Next Generation Internet, and grouped them according to themes. Based on the discovered areas, we identified a number of key umbrella topics in each iteration of the analysis. This is a subjective part of the study: other researchers may interpret the results differently. However, the raw results have been published at Zenodo (Gyódi et al., 2021a), enabling the analysis outside our team.

⁸ <https://policy.delabapps.eu/#OB4>

Figure 10. Identified key umbrella topics in 2020

5.3 Co-occurrence analysis

Co-occurrences were calculated for selected terms from the previous list of trending terms. The selection of terms was an interpretive process: those terms were selected that are representative of the general umbrella topics. For these terms (“analysed terms”), the most common “co-occurring” terms have been calculated. The terms co-occur if they are present in the same article, not necessarily in the same sentence or paragraph. Similarly to the analysis of term frequencies, the process ends with lists of co-occurring terms, sorted by the co-occurrence scores. Following this algorithmic process, interpretive analysis decides which terms among the top co-occurrences are summarised in the presentations. Therefore, the final results reflect our subjective opinions. However, we also publish all raw results at Zenodo for further analysis (Gyódi et al. 2021b).

Figure 11. Example for co-occurrences

5.4 Sentiment analysis

Sentiment analysis is a field of text-mining focused on identifying the emotions in documents. We are interested in extracting the general attitude towards policies and technologies: our aim is to determine whether a subject is discussed in a rather positive or negative way.

The sentiment analysis has been prepared using VADER, an open-source lexicon and rule-based sentiment analysis tool (Hutto et al., 2014). VADER assigns a score for text data with values between -1 (extremely negative) and +1 (extremely positive).

The same words which have been chosen for the co-occurrence analysis were selected for the sentiment analysis. We presented two analyses: the average monthly sentiment of paragraphs containing the selected terms, and co-occurrences with the most positive and negative sentiments.

Similarly to the previous steps, the final most positive and most negative co-occurrences were selected in an interpretive process. with raw results published at Zenodo (Gyódi et al., 2021c).

Figure 12. Example for sentiment analysis for the term “greenhouse gas ”(up - average sentiment scores over time, down - most positive / negative co-occurrences)

5.5 Topic modelling

The first three steps of the analysis provide a funnel: from all terms present in the documents, the trending ones are captured and the relationships between them are explored. Topic modelling is orthogonal to these steps: it can be omitted from trend analysis. The aim of topic modelling is the general identification of topics in documents, irrespective whether the topic is trending over time. Therefore, topic modelling is more suited to the second set of methods presented by us as topic mapping. In fact, the experimentation with topic modelling provided the foundations for the creation of the topic mapping pipeline. We have included topic modelling in the trend analysis pipeline as an additional analysis that may capture insights not picked up by the previous tools.

Topic modelling assumes that documents, such as news articles, contain various distinguishable topics. The other assumption is that topics contain characteristic vocabularies,

e.g. the social media topic is described by the words Facebook, Twitter etc. Latent Dirichlet Allocation is a popular topic modelling method due to its ease of use, flexibility and interpretable results. LDA has been proposed by Blei et al. (2003), based on Bayesian statistics.

As part of the trend analysis pipeline, we used LDA to discover topics in selected samples of documents. Following the identification of trending terms, we created wide umbrella topics that were the basis of further analyses (co-occurrences, sentiment analysis and topic modelling). We prepared LDA analysis on articles relevant to the umbrella topics: the articles had to include trending keywords related to the umbrella topic. The selection of keywords combined the algorithmic and interpretive approach: first, a seed list of keywords representative of the umbrella topic was prepared. Next, all trending terms that included the root form of these seed words (e.g. root form of 'cryptocurrency' is 'cryptocurr') were identified. Finally, the list was checked manually to exclude irrelevant terms (e.g. '5G' is included in various technical terms, such as '75GB'). Following the identification of article samples, for each sample the LDA was performed and the results were summarised.

LDA provides the topic-document distributions (how relevant is a topic, how frequently it is present in documents) and the word-topic distributions (how relevant is a word in a topic). In our interactive presentations, we published interactive visualizations that included all discovered topics and topic-words⁹. This format facilitates the user's own interpretation of topics. In our reports, we also prepared a qualitative interpretation of these results, naming the topics and presenting the most relevant words in tables.

SUSTAINABILITY & CLIMATE CRISIS

⁹ E.g. https://fwd.delabapps.eu/topic_modelling.html

Figure 13. Example for LDA

5.6 Topic mapping

The topic mapping methodology originates from our topic modelling work presented in the trend analysis. As demonstrated by our reports, LDA has been useful in indicating what kind of topics are discussed in news articles. It served as a last step in exploring the context of emerging trends: following the identification of trending keywords and selection of emerging umbrella topics with expert analysis, LDA complemented the insights of the co-occurrence and sentiment analyses carried out for each umbrella topic.

However, the potential of LDA is limited: while the user gains an overview of topics with characteristic terms, its use for further analysis is restricted. Therefore, we began to work on an alternative pipeline that extracts more information on topics of interest than LDA. We shifted our focus towards supporting qualitative analysis with a way to help users organise documents and read only the ones that are relevant for them. The topic mapping pipeline not only explores keywords included in documents, but also facilitates the analysis and summary of the documents.

Figure 14. Topic mapping pipeline

Our first effort combined LDA with an algorithm called t-SNE. t-SNE can be used to visualise high-dimensional data in 2D: in our case, documents are distributed in space based on their semantic similarity. t-SNE has been introduced by Van der Maaten and Hinton (2008) and followed multiple attempts to find a dimensionality reduction algorithm that preserves local structure. This means that observations that are close to each other in the input high-dimensional space are also placed close to each other in the output low-dimensional space, but separate to other articles, e.g. articles about bitcoin should form a separate cloud to articles about AI, but be close to articles about blockchain usage in smart contracts.

The philosophy behind topic mapping is different from trend analysis: while trend analysis focuses on finding emerging keywords and exploring them, topic mapping captures all areas of discussion. Therefore, the first step in the analysis is the definition of wide areas the researcher is interested in, e.g. issues related to privacy or misinformation. In our analyses based on topic mapping, we focused on six wide umbrella topics selected together with our partners from the project.

Next, we compiled a dataset of online documents corresponding to the six topics. Instead of selecting a few websites and collecting all articles published by them, we focused on diversity of sources and maximising the number of publishers and types of documents (news articles, blog posts, opinion pieces, events etc). For this reason, documents shared on social media platforms were collected matching search criteria for each umbrella topic. Similarly to the selection of the umbrella topics, the search criteria were also assigned in an interpretive process.

We used t-SNE – an algorithmic step – to map articles in two dimensions: articles close to each other on the map cover the same issue. Next, we have examined the text and titles of articles to select the most relevant clusters. In an interpretive process, we have named these clusters and prepared short descriptions.

These topics are highlighted on the maps: the arrow is indicating the subject and the location of the article cluster.

Finally, we also prepared deep dives for selected issues based on the maps to showcase the potential of the methodology. The deep dives are based on the articles presented in the article clusters. We focused on areas, where the results highlighted not only the underlying challenges, but also policy and technological solutions. These deep dives are interpretive: other researchers may choose other clusters and topics for analysis. As all interactive maps are publicly available¹⁰, all users can verify the clusters and explore the articles. The global nature of the challenges means that a wide range of discussions and debates take place across the world in different languages. Therefore, by restricting the analysis only to English, we might be losing valuable country-specific information on the analysed topics. For this reason, we also prepared a complementary analysis for articles in German, Polish, Spanish and Portuguese.

¹⁰ ngitopics.delabapps.eu

PRIVACY, IDENTITY & DATA GOVERNANCE

Figure 15. Example of topic mapping

References

- Beaulieu, A., & Leonelli, S. (2021). *Data and Society: A Critical Introduction*. SAGE.
- Barron, A. T. J., Huang, J., Spang, R. L., & DeDeo, S. (2018). Individuals, institutions, and innovation in the debates of the French Revolution. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 115(18), 4607–4612. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1717729115>
- Blei, D. M., Ng, A. Y., & Jordan, M. I. (2003). Latent Dirichlet Allocation. *The Journal of Machine Learning Research*, 3, 993–1022.
- Blondel, V. D., Guillaume, J. L., Lambiotte, R., & Lefebvre, E. (2008). Fast unfolding of communities in large networks. *Journal of statistical mechanics: theory and experiment*, 2008(10), P10008.
- Breznau, N., Rinke, E., Wuttke, A., Adem, M., Adriaans, J., Alvarez-Benjumea, A., ... Nguyen, H. H. V. (2021, March 24). Observing Many Researchers Using the Same Data and Hypothesis Reveals a Hidden Universe of Uncertainty. <https://doi.org/10.31222/osf.io/cd5j9>
- Chang, H., 2004. *Inventing temperature: Measurement and scientific progress*. Oxford University Press.
- Christensen, K., Kim, J. Y., Tveen, M. H., & Nissen, I. A. (2021). Eight topics for building a human-centric internet. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5795259>
- Cottica, A., Hassoun, A., Manca, M., Vallet, J. and Melançon, G., 2020. Semantic Social Networks: A Mixed Methods Approach to Digital Ethnography. *Field Methods*, 32(3), pp.274-290.
- Cottica, A., Hassoun, A., Manca, M., Vallet, J., & Melançon, G. (2020). Semantic Social Networks: A Mixed Methods Approach to Digital Ethnography. *Field Methods*, 32(3), 274-290.
- Decuyper, A., Browet, A., Traag, V., Blondel, V. D., & Delvenne, J. C. (2016). Clean up or mess up: the effect of sampling biases on measurements of degree distributions in mobile phone datasets. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1609.09413*.
- Eagle, N., Macy, M., & Claxton, R. (2010). Network diversity and economic development. *Science*, 328(5981), 1029-1031.
- Ghoniem, M., Fekete, J. D., & Castagliola, P. (2005). On the readability of graphs using node-link and matrix-based representations: a controlled experiment and statistical analysis. *Information Visualization*, 4(2), 114-135.
- Glaser, B. G., Strauss, A. L., & Strutzel, E. (1968). The discovery of grounded theory; strategies for qualitative research. *Nursing research*, 17(4), 364.

- Gyódi, K., Nawaro, Ł., Paliński, M., & Wilamowski, M. (2019). Informing Policy with Text Mining: Technological Change and Social Challenges. Available at SSRN: <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3362487>
- Gyódi, K., Nawaro, L., & Paliński, P. (2021a). Keyword frequencies in popular tech media (01.2016-04.2021) [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5788431>
- Gyódi, K., Nawaro, L., & Paliński, P. (2021b). Co-occurrences of trending keywords in popular tech media (01.2016-04.2021) [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5788439>
- Gyódi, K., Nawaro, L., & Paliński, P. (2021c). Sentiment analysis of tech media articles using VADER package and co-occurrence analysis (01.2016-04.2021) [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5788439>
- Hassoun, A., Cottica, A., Sim, K. & Schulte, L. (2021). The Next Generation Internet: a large-scale ethnography. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5741917>
- Honnibal, M., & Montani, I. (2017). Natural language understanding with Bloom embeddings, convolutional neural networks and incremental parsing. Unpublished Software Application. <https://spacy.io>.
- Hutto, C.J. & Gilbert, E.E. (2014). VADER: A Parsimonious Rule-based Model for Sentiment Analysis of Social Media Text. Eighth International Conference on Weblogs and Social Media (ICWSM-14). Ann Arbor, MI, June 2014.
- Leonelli, S. (2019). What distinguishes data from models?. *European Journal for Philosophy of Science*, 9(2), 22.
- Melançon, G. (2006, May). Just how dense are dense graphs in the real world? A methodological note. In *Proceedings of the 2006 AVI workshop on BEyond time and errors: novel evaluation methods for information visualization* (pp. 1-7).
- Munzner, T. (2014) *Visualization Analysis and Design*, Routledge
- Nielbo, K. L., Vahlstrup, P. B., Bechmann, A., & Gao, J. (2020). Trend Reservoir Detection: Minimal Persistence and Resonant Behavior of Trends in Social Media. *Proceedings of the Conference on Computational Humanities Research*.
- Nissen, I. A., Mortensen, M. D., Sala, M., Walter, J. G., Charquero-Ballester, M., Sørensen, M. H., Nielbo, K. L., & Bechmann, A. (2021). Social media analysis with a focus on human rights on the internet. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5795341>
- Silberzahn, R., Uhlmann, E. L., Martin, D. P., Anselmi, P., Aust, F., Awtrey, E., ... & Nosek, B. A. (2018). Many analysts, one data set: Making transparent how variations in analytic choices affect results. *Advances in Methods and Practices in Psychological Science*, 1(3), 337-356.

Van der Maaten, L., & Hinton, G. (2008). Visualizing data using t-SNE. *Journal of machine learning research*, 9(11)